

**XORAZM VOHASI SHAROITIDA OQAVA SUVLARNI TOZALASHDA
SUVO'TLARDAN FOYDALANISH**

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Annotatsiya: Tezisdagi suv o'simliklarini (*Azolla caroliniana*) oqava suvlarda, ekologik jihatdan noqulay sharoitlarida etishtirish natijalari keltirilgan. Ushbu o'simlikni etishtirishdan oldin va keyingi oqava suvlarining tahliliy natijalari keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: oqava suv; ifloslantiruvchi moddalar; biogen elementlar; suvo'tlar; *Azolla caroliniana*.

Аннотация: В тезисе представлены результаты выращивания водных растений (*Azolla caroliniana*) в сточных водах в экологически неблагоприятных условиях. Представлены результаты анализа сточных вод до и после выращивания этого растения.

Ключевые слова: сточные воды; загрязняющие вещества; биогенные элементы; водоросли; *Азолла Каролиниана*.

Annotation: The thesis presents the results of the cultivation of aquatic plants (*Azolla caroliniana*) in wastewater under ecologically unfavorable conditions. Analytical results of wastewater before and after cultivation of this plant are presented.

Key words: wastewater; pollutants; biogenic elements; algae; *Azolla caroliniana*.

Tabiiy resurslardan oqilona foydalanish, xususan, chuchuk suvdan oqilona foydalanish bugungi kunning dolzarb muammolaridan biridir. So'ngi yillarda yer yuzi aholisi soni keskin ortib borayotganligi sababli inson omilining chuchuk suvga bo'lgan ehtiyojini qondirishda, xususan ekinlarni sug'orishda, sanoat korxonalarini toza suv bilan taminlashda yetarlicha muammolar mavjud. Mavjud muammoni hal etishning ustuvor yo'nalishlaridan - suv havzalariga oqava suvlarni tushirishni kamaytirish, chuqur tozalash texnologiyalarini (oziq moddalarni olib tashlash) joriy etish va oqava suvlarni tozalash sifatini oshirishdir. Oqava suvlarning tarkibida har hil organik ifloslantiruvchi moddalar, biogen elementlar, uglevodorodlar, og'ir metallar, mineral suspenziyalar kabi o'simlik ildizi o'zlashtiraolmaydigan biologik va kimyoviy chiqindilar mavjud. Oqava suvlarni tozalash muvaffaqiyatli amalga oshirilsa yuqorida aytib o'tilgan muammolarni qisman bo'lsada bartaraf etishga muvaffaq bo'lamiz. Bunda biz suvo'tlardan foydalanishimiz mumkin. Barcha o'simliklar biogen moddalarga, hayotiy metallarga(Fe, Zn, Cu, Mn, Mo, Co) doimiy zarur. Polshada oqava suvlarni fitoremediatsiya qilishda keng tarqalgan suv osti va suzuvchi suv o'simliklaridan *Eloдея canadensis* L. , suv osti shoxli o'ti *Ceratophyllum demersum* L. , *Myriophyllum spicatum* L. , *Potamogetonaceae* , kichik *Lemna* L. va *Azolla caroliniana*dan foydalanish yo'lga qo'yilgan.

Azolla caroliniana juda tez o'sadigan suzuvchi suv qirqqulog'idir. U ko'llar yuzasiga tarqala oladi va bir necha oy ichida suv yuzasini to'liq qoplaydi. Har bir o'simlikning kengligi 1-2 sm, qirralari pushti, to'q sariq yoki qizil rangga bo'yalgan, erkin shoxlanadigan va o'sishi bilan kichikroq bo'laklarga bo'linadigan suvo'tidir. U mo'tadil iqlim sharoitida yaxshi rivojlanadi, qishda o'ladi, suv ostida joylashgan kurtaklar omon qoladi. So'nggi paytlarda *Azolla* ko'plab Osiyo mamlakatlarida sholi va baliq etishtirish tizimlari bo'yicha tadqiqotlarda ozuqa va/yoki o'g'it sifatida tobora ko'proq foydalanilmoqda.

Azolla suvning kislotaligi – pH ko'rsatkichiga ham tasr ko'rsatadi:

Oqava suvda pH=7,11-7,21;

Azolla o'stirilgan oqava suvda pH=6,11;

Quyida *Azolla caroliniana*ning kaloniya va yakka holdagi rasmlari keltirilgan:

1-rasm

2-rasm

1-, 2-rasmlar. Azollaning kaloniyasi.

3-rasm

4-rasm

3-, 4-rasmlar. Yakka holdagi Azolla.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR RO'YXATI:

1. Абасова Д.К., Боровкова О.А., и др. Ежегодник ВОДА В ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОЙ АЗИИ И МИРЕ 2018. НИЦ МКВК. Ташкентю-2019.-326с
2. Lumpkin T. A. and Plucknett D. L. (1980) Azolla: botany, physiology and use as a green manure. *Econ. Bot.* 34, 111-153.
3. Masnur Radjabov, Anvar Tadjiev, Davronbek Yavkachev, Daniyori Kalandarov, Denis Otanazarov, Xudaybergan Xudayberganov, and Nigora Ibragimova. A promising direction for improving the environmental situation at the Aral Sea. *Web of Conferences* 431. 2023.-P.1-9.

4. <http://flower.onego.ru/voda/azolla.html>
5. Фазлиев, Ж. Ш. (2023, October). ТОМЧИЛАТИБ СУҒОРИШ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯСИ ОРҚАЛИ СУҒОРИЛГАН ОЛМА БОҒЛАРИНИНГ ТУПРОҚ АГРОКИМЁВИЙ КЎРСАТКИЧЛАРИ. In Proceedings of International Conference on Educational Discoveries and Humanities (Vol. 2, No. 11, pp. 19-23).
6. Фазлиев, Ж. Ш. (2019). EFFICIENCY OF USE OF CLAY WATER WITH DROP IRRIGATION. ЖУРНАЛ АГРО ПРОЦЕССИНГ, (4).
7. Xudayev, I. J., & Tojiyev, S. M. (2023). NAMLATGICH-BLOKLARDAN HOSIL QILINGAN EKTRANLI EGATLARDAN G‘O‘ZANI SUG‘ORISH TEXNOLOGIYASI. In Uz-Conferences (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 514-519).
8. Худайев, И., & Фазлиев, Ж. ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ КАПЕЛЬНОГО ОРОШЕНИЯ САДОВ И ВИНОГРАДНИКОВ. JURNALI, 176
9. Fazliyev, J. (2017). Drip irrigation technology in gardens. Интернаука. Science Journal, 7(11).
10. Fazliyev, J. (2018). Modern irrigation methods for gardens. Science, 22, 24-26.
11. Фазлиев, Ж. Ш., & Баратов, С. С. (2014). ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ГЛИНИСТОЙ ВОДЫ ПРИ КАПЕЛЬНОМ ОРОШЕНИИ. The Way of Science, (4), 77.
12. Fazliyev, J. EFFICIENCY OF APPLYING THE WATER-SAVING IRRIGATION TECHNOLOGIES IN IRRIGATED FARMING «ИНТЕРНАУКА» Science Journal № 21 (103) June 2019 г.
13. Khudaev, I., & Fazliev, J. (2022). Water-saving irrigation technology in the foothill areas in the south of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Современные инновации, системы и технологии, 2(2), 0301-0309
14. Фазлиев, Ж. Ш. (2017). Боғларда томчилатиб суғориш технологияси. Интернаука, (7-3), 71-73.
15. Худайев , И., & Тожиев , Ш. (2023). БОҒ ВА УЗЎМЗОРЛАРДА ТОМЧИЛАТИБ СУҒОРИШ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯСИНИ ЖОРИЙ ҚИЛИШНИНГ САМАРАДОРЛИГИ. Talqin Va Tadqiqotlar, 1(1). извлечено от <https://talqinvatadqiqotlar.uz/index.php/tvt/article/view/220>
16. Фазлиев Жамолiddин, Тожиев Шерзод, & Холиқов Шарифбек. (2024). СПОСОБЫ ЭКОНОМИИ ВОДНЫХ РЕСУРСОВ В САДАХ. Uz-Conferences, 1(1), 520–525. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/110>
17. J.Sh.Fazliyev., Sh.M.Tojiyev., Sh.D.Khalikov. (2024). EFFICIENCY OF USE OF CLAY WATER WITH DROP IRRIGATION. Uz-Conferences, 1(1), 504–509. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/107>.
18. I.J.Xudayev, I.J.Xudayev, & Sh.M.Tojiyev. (2024). NAMLATGICH-BLOKLARDAN HOSIL QILINGAN EKTRANLI EGATLARDAN G‘O‘ZANI SUG‘ORISH TEXNOLOGIYASI. Uz-Conferences, 1(1), 514–519. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/109>
19. Khamidov, M. K., Juraev, U. A., Buriev, X. B., Juraev, A. K., Saksonov, U. S., Sharifov, F. K., & Isabaev, K. T. (2023, February). Efficiency of drip irrigation technology of cotton in saline soils of Bukhara oasis. In IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science (Vol. 1138, No. 1, p. 012007). IOP Publishing.
20. Sharifov Firdavs, & Mirzamurotov Mirshod. (2024). G‘O‘ZA O‘SIMLIGINI YETISHTIRISHDA SUV TEJAMKOR SUG‘ORISH TEXNOLOGIYALARINI QO‘LLASH. Uz-Conferences, 1(1), 461–464. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/98>
21. Sattorovich, S. U., & Qobil o‘g‘li, S. F. (2022). BUG ‘DOY O‘SIMLIGI VA DONINING XALQ XO‘JALIGIDA BUGUNGI KUNDAGI AHAMIYATI.
22. Xamrayev Kamol, Sharifov Firdavs, & Yusupova Oynura. (2024). TUPROQ SHO‘RINI YUVISHDA BIOSOLVENT BIRIKMASINI TUPROQ SUV-TUZ MUVOZANATIGA TA‘SIRI. Uz-Conferences, 1(1), 458–460. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/97>
23. Shodiev, Z. O., Inoyatov, I. S., & Shodiev, N. S. (2020). NATURAL PASTE AND ITS VALUE TODAY. In *Эффективность применения инновационных технологий и техники в сельском и водном хозяйстве* (pp. 198-200).
24. Shaxrilloevich, I. I. (2023). DIDACTIC CONDITIONS FOR THE PREPARATION OF STUDENTS OF VOCATIONAL EDUCATION FOR PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY BASED ON AN INNOVATIVE APPROACH. *Academia Repository*, 4(10), 142-145.

25. Шахриллоевич П (2021). Педагогические условия формирования готовности выпускников вузов к трудоустройству. *ACADEMICIA: МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ МНОГОДИСЦИПЛИНАРНЫЙ ИССЛЕДОВАТЕЛЬСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ*, 11 (1), 881-884.
26. Ochilovich, S. Z. (2020, September). Inoyatov Ikrom Shaxriloyevich, Shodiyev Ne'matjon Sadirovich. Tabiiy uyulovlar va uning bugungi kundagi ahamiyati. In *Эффективность применение инновационных технологий и техники в сельском и водном хозяйстве» международная научно-практическая онлайн-конференция* (pp. 25-26).
27. Ikrom, I. (2023). KASBIY TAYYORGARLIKNING RIVOJLANISH DINAMIKASI BO'YICHA PEDAGOGIK TAJRIBA-SINOV ISHLARI NATIJALARINING TAHLILI. In *Uz-Conferences* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 626-633).
28. EUsarov, J., JEsnaev, N., OKhachimov, J., ISaidova, D., ShInoyatov, I., & SShodiev, N. (2022). THE SOCIAL SIGNIFICANCE OF CREATING A MECHANISM OF PSYCHOLOGICAL STUDY OF THE CHILDRENS SPIRIT IN CRISIS FAMILIES. *NeuroQuantology*, 20(16), 4614.
29. Musinovich, S. M. (2023, June). DRIP IRRIGATION INTENSIVE APPLE ORCHARDS AND SEASONAL WATER CONSUMPTION. In *Proceedings of Scientific Conference on Multidisciplinary Studies* (Vol. 2, No. 6, pp. 8-14).
30. Саримсаков, М. М. (2023, May). СПОСОБЫ ПОЛИВА И УРОЖАЙНОСТЬ ИНТЕНСИВНЫХ ЯБЛОНЕВЫХ САДОВ. In *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE* (Vol. 2, No. 14, pp. 173-175).
31. Shodiev, N. S. (2022). USE OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN PREPARING ENGINEERING STUDENTS FOR PROJECT-CONSTRUCTION ACTIVITY. *Экономика и социум*, (10-2 (101)), 167-169.
32. Sadirovich, S. N. (2022). The Significance of Problem Situation Assignments in Teaching the Science of Machine Details. *Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science*, 3(8), 30-32.
33. Shodiyev Ziyodullo Ochilovich, & Shodiyev Nematjon Sadirovich. (2022). KINEMATIC STUDY OF FLAT BASE MECHANISMS. *E Conference Zone*, 61-69. Retrieved from <https://www.econferencezone.org/index.php/ecz/article/view/888>
34. Shodiyev Ziyodullo Ochilovich, & Shodiyev Nematjon Sadirovich. (2022). STUDY OF THE EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON THE DRYING PROCESS OF COTTON RAW MATERIALS. *Conferencea*, 47-50. Retrieved from <https://conferencea.org/index.php/conferences/article/view/295>
35. Shodiev, N. S. (2022). " PREPARING ENGINEERING STUDENTS FOR DESIGNCONSTRUCTION ACTIVITY THROUGH TEACHING" MACHINE DETAILS". *International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education*, 14(7).
36. Ochilovich, S. Z., Abduganievich, D. N., Nematovich, S. S., & Sadirovich, S. N. (2021). EFFECT OF FORCES ON AIR CONVEYING DEVICES AND NETWORK ON COTTON SEED QUALITY. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(12), 771-775.
37. Nematovich, S. S., Abduganievich, D. N., & Sadirovich, S. N. (2021). TECHNOLOGY OF PRODUCTION OF CERAMIC MATERIALS AND ITS VALUE TODAY. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(12), 768-770.
38. Ochilovich, S. Z., Abdug'aniyevich, D. N., Ne'matovich, S. S., & Sadirovich, S. N. M. (2021). Methods Of Kinematic Study of Flat Base Mechanisms. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 3, 208-214.
39. Садир Нематович Шодиев1, Неъматжон Садирович Шодиев2. (2024). ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ ВЛИЯНИЯ ЗАБИВАЕМОСТИ ТРУБОК РАДИАТОРА НА ТЕПЛОВОЕ СОСТОЯНИЯ ДВИГАТЕЛЯ. *Uz-Conferences*, 1(1), 145-151. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/32>
40. Shodiyev Ne'matjon. (2024). INTEGRATIV YONDASHUV ASOSIDA UMUMKASBIY FANLARNI O'QITISHNING ZAMONAVIY TEXNOLOGIYALARI. *Uz-Conferences*, 1(1), 945-950. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/195>
41. Shodiyev Ne'matjon. (2024). TEXNIKA OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA UMUMKASBIY FANLARNI AXBOROT TA'LIM MUHITIDA O'QITISHNING MUHIM YO'NALISHLARI. *Uz-Conferences*, 1(1), 938-944. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/194>